

An Extensive Reading, Graded Reader Programme at Tokyo University of Science

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Abstract

Any educational context evolves over time. In this regard, the English language teaching curriculum at Tokyo University of Science (TUS) is no different. With this report, we take into consideration the background to the study of English in Japan, the reasons for recent national and institutional policy reform and the repercussions in the teaching of reading. In this regard, we review the literature regarding what constitutes best practice in the English as a Foreign Language (EFL) context of Japan. Furthermore, we analyse the benefits and pitfalls of introducing first- and second-year students to an online extensive reading programme.

Keywords: Policy reform, Reading instruction, Extensive Reading, Graded readers

Introduction

Any educational context evolves over time. In this regard, the English language teaching curriculum at Tokyo University of Science (TUS) is no different. With this report, we take into consideration the background to the study of English in Japan, the reasons for recent national and institutional policy reform and the repercussions in the teaching of reading. Thus, we review the literature regarding what constitutes best practice in the English as a Foreign Language (EFL) context of Japan. Furthermore, we analyse the benefits and pitfalls of introducing first- and second-year students to an online extensive reading programme.

Reform in English Education Policy

As a result of English language education at the secondary level focussing on university entrance examinations, a typical first-year student at TUS will almost certainly have received information passively within a transmission of knowledge from teacher to student (Abe, 2013; Bax, 2003).

Such a system of education precludes learning as a 'negotiation of meaning', where students engage in discussions, express opinions, or in group problem solving between people in spoken discourse (Varonis and Gass, 1985). To that end, prior to entry, a typical first-year student at TUS tends to have achieved a high level of knowledge of English structure but a low competency in oral communication (Sakamoto, 2012; Aspinall, 2006; Butler and Iino, 2005).

The recognition of poor English oral communication skills, by policymakers, has resulted in policy reform with reference to the 'internationalisation' of higher education (Numata, 2013). The internationalisation of higher education in Japan has evolved over the past decades to encompass:

(1) Creating a more recognisable international identity so that

opinions and ideas of the Japanese state be better understood in the international arena (Whitsed and Wright, 2013; Kobayashi, 2011; Kawai, 2007).

(2) Creating a workforce able to conduct business and research in English at the same level as their peers in other nations (Keidanren, 2016; Grove, 2012; Inui and Kojima, 2012; MEXT, 2014; Denman, 2014; Lo Bianco, 2013).

(3) Creating greater cultural and social understanding between Japan and other nations (Bradford, 2013; Takagi, 2009; Butler and Iino, 2005).

(4) Enhancing student-centred learning and critical thinking (DeWaelche, 2015; Yonezawa, 2011).

Due to the instigation of policies which are designed to fulfil these notions, scholars suggest that a host of complex and dynamic factors exist within 'individuals, policies or practices, within the classroom, the school, the educational system, or society as a whole' (Watanabe, 2004; Wall, 1997, p. 291).

One of these notions is to be found in the discourse of World Englishes. Kachru (1985) places Japan in the outermost of three concentric circles where English is engaged with as a foreign language. Within this concept, a variety of systems have developed in separate regions of the world regarding the way English is taught and learned in primary, secondary and higher education (Phan, 2013). In the group of countries in which Japan is situated, although English is evident in day-to-day life, its use is mostly 'decorative' and 'atmospheric' (Rowland, 2016, Backhaus 2014). And yet, compared with other countries in the expanding circle such as China and Korea, Japan struggles to gain parity on the international stage in terms of English ability.

Another notion is the educational context of the learner – in this case an English as a Foreign Language (EFL)/expanding circle context. In this report, we take the premise that a learners' 'culture-specific values and beliefs may clash with values and beliefs threaten[ing] cultural identity and integrity and produc[ing] consequences of which the

native culture does not approve' (Hu, 2002). Moreover, we follow Tjeldvoll (2011) who asserts that the type of system of learning practiced in such 'Confucian lands' as Japan, has been greatly influenced by the emphasising of the study of key historical texts by those who go on to become 'model' members of society.

A third emerges with the new priority being placed on improving students' oral communication competence in higher education institutes in Japan through innovations made in English language curricula (Humphries and Burns, 2015). Such institutions are moving away from receptive lesson activities that focus on teacher-controlled translation of high-level English texts into Japanese; and are moving towards a focus on improving the proficiency of students' through a greater use of more level-appropriate texts (Jennings, 2018).

With reference to the four factors (above) connected to the 'internationalisation' of higher education institutions in Japan, English language teaching policy reform in TUS should be seen as being embedded in a larger web of interdependent concepts outside its control (Waters, 2014; Larsen-Freeman, 2013; Lo Bianco, 2013; Kennedy and Kennedy, 1996). In this regard, as with the case of introducing innovative practices, such as a graded reader program, explained in the next section, there is also a need to make internationally recognised best-practice – in the acquisition of a foreign language applicable in a local context (Jones et al., 2016; Stambach, 2016; Cha and Ham, 2011; Bjork, 2010; Knight, 2008; Block and Cameron, 2002).

In this section it was reported that higher education institutions in Japan are currently going through a step-change with reference to how English is taught and learned. Namely, a move away from receptive activities using high-level texts; towards activities which are informed by level-appropriate texts and require students to use 'active' skills such as those which are useful in consensus-building. The teaching of reading skills in TUS has, typically consisted of receptive activities using high-level texts from which translation is required. However, in order to fulfil global, national and institutional policy regarding English education, an

Extensive Reading, Graded Reader Programme was established in 2019 at TUS, Noda Campus.

The following section outlines how a background to reading instruction is followed by an in-depth look at the merits of Extensive Reading, the Graded Reader Programme and its trial implementation.

Background to reading instruction

In considering the instruction of reading in an EFL context several questions must be asked. Firstly, how can we accurately describe what reading is as a process? That is to say, what happens when we pick up a book, newspaper, or click on a website or our personal email and begin *reading*? Secondly, how is learning reading different for first- and second-year university students in the context of TUS?

In the 1970s, Goodman (1975, p. 5) promoted the model of the reading process for second or foreign language learners as a "psycholinguistic guessing game". In this view, skilled readers become adept at considering what will follow a given word, phrase or clause. This kind of skill develops after many hundreds of hours of reading; or in other words, after extensive reading.

Partly owing to the dominance of behavioural psychology, which eschewed psychoanalytic extrapolations of the inner mental life of the subject – and the subsequent shift towards and development of psycholinguistic models (Samuels and Kamil, 1995) – in the first half of the 20th century, no detailed attempts at describing the reading process had been made. At that time, reading, whether silently or out loud, appears to have been merely regarded as the process of mentally turning letters into recognizable sounds (Goodman, 1975). These sounds, when put together, form known words, comprehensible sentences, structured paragraphs and, finally, complete texts. As a result, there seems to have been a notion of the reader's mind as a passive vessel into which information was poured.

To that end, Anthony (1946) notes the tedium and ineffectiveness of

the grammar translation method typically used in the intensive reading instruction of her time, and, frustratingly, still used by some teachers today who are unable to free themselves from these antiquated teaching practices. Coleman (1930) likewise notes that reading instruction is limited to intensive reading of very short text passages (Coleman, 1930) and that the idea that reading instruction is equivalent to translation and that translation of the classics is a necessary first stage through which beginner English language learners must pass (Coleman, 1930, p. 102).

Intensive and Extensive Reading

Intensive reading involves the close examination of short texts. Instruction in this area involves the introduction of specific vocabulary. With intensive reading the teacher chooses a reading passage of story and leaves the students to study the language of the text; focusing on word meaning, applying reading vocabulary, grammar, and other skills and strategies. Extensive reading, on the other hand, is a highly individualised approach to reading improvement. In order to become fluent, competent readers in ESL/EFL contexts, students develop the habit of reading massive amounts in English at linguistically appropriate levels (Mikulecky, 2011).

In terms of Extensive Reading, Anthony (1946) writes that the learner must also “enjoy the reading” to increase the likelihood that they will continue (Anthony, 1946, p. 499). The importance of enjoying reading is but one in a list of qualities that define an extensive reading learning context.

These are as follows:

- (1) The material is easy to read.
- (2) A wide range of topics can be accessed.
- (3) Learners freely select the books they read.
- (4) Learners read as much as they can.
- (5) Learners read for enjoyment, fact-finding and general comprehension.

- (6) Readers read with object of reading and not for a subsequent goal.
- (7) Speed is faster than normal or with intensive reading.
- (8) Learners read individually and silently.
- (9) Teachers act as guides, monitors and facilitators.
- (10) The teacher models the role of the good reader.
(Day, 2015; Day & Bamford, 2002)

Grabe and Stoller (2002) note that despite the many differing conclusions in research on reading instruction, the importance of extensive reading remains one of the constants among recommended teaching practices in L2 learning environments.

Research findings from many researchers in the field of L2 reading instruction make a strong case for extensive reading. Benefits of extensive reading include increased motivation, comprehension and reading speed. In addition, reading extensively has also been shown to improve literacy skills, grammar skills as well as listening and writing abilities. What is more, extensive reading promotes conceptual knowledge growth, and better reasoning skills (Grabe, 2009). In illustration, rather than referring to the dictionary for every unknown word, learners must “guess the meaning” by considering the “context” (Anthony, 1946, p. 499) in which the words are used; that is, the surrounding words.

In the context of TUS, some teachers with backgrounds in literature have pointed out that graded reader versions of literary classics may not adequately convey the intended meaning of the author. The main reason for this view is that traditionally, the introduction of literature has been presented using exemplary texts.

However, for the purposes of this report, we take the premise that notwithstanding genuinely novel and enlightening use of literature in the EFL classroom such as Widdowson’s stylistics (1975), teachers should remember that, in the context of TUS, the express goal of reading classes is to develop students’ English reading skills, rather than make them knowledgeable about British and American literature. Instead, students should be given the freedom to choose books (from a level-

appropriate selection) that interest them, so that they not only increase their vocabulary, but they also develop a sense of autonomy which will enable some of them to become lifelong readers.

We take the view that best practice in the EFL context means teachers shifting their practice towards ways of reading instruction that would motivate learners and free them from sloughing through books word-by-word with a dictionary (Waring, n.d.). Although notions of the efficacy of the exemplary text in the EFL reading class continues to be a staple in the EFL context, policy reform at a range of levels has led to teachers implementing lesson activities which allow students to read extensively. The following sections move on to explain how such activities have been implemented in TUS.

Implementing a Graded Reader Programme

In an extensive reading class, students all have books and spend their time doing sustained silent reading (Grabe, 2009). The duration of the reading time may differ from lesson to lesson, but it has been shown that 30 minutes can be effective. It is important to note that students' reading skills cannot be expected to increase much if they are only reading during class time. The class time allocated to sustained silent reading is a means for introducing the idea that reading may be enjoyable and satisfying for students and that they ought to consider reading outside of class. Certainly, the classroom is not only a space for silent reading. It is a training ground for autonomous reading outside the classroom as well.

Graded Readers

Graded Readers are books in which the language has been simplified to levels of difficulty appropriate for second language learners at various levels of reading proficiency. These books are produced by nearly all EFL textbook publishing houses. They cover a large variety of genres

including biographies of famous people, descriptions of famous cities, discussions of science topics, explanations or how-to books, and classics of literature (Waring, n.d.). Thus, graded readers present written discourse in a wide range of rhetorical modes. Another important feature of graded readers is their use of headwords (Mikulecky, 2011), which are drawn from each publisher's list of recommended words and idioms recommended by results from research in the field of corpus linguistics by virtue of the frequency of use (Dongkwan and Chon, 2011).

Of course, there were no graded readers in 1926, nor in 1946. And until 2018 there were no graded readers in the TUS library, despite the fact that large graded libraries have become practically ubiquitous throughout Japan. Upon joining the faculty in 2013, Gann and Jennings recognized this shortcoming and made plans to ameliorate the situation. It was concluded, based on the number of students enrolled in reading classes, that by the end of 2021 the library should hold roughly 2,700 graded readers.

Concurrent to this, Gann had recruited a number of full-time and part-time teachers to use graded readers to form the basis of lesson activities, so that in 2019, in both the spring and fall terms, 15 sections of Reading and Writing classes were to be taught using extensive reading instructional techniques.

MReader

A popular online learning environment, mreader.org, is being used in the Extensive Reading Graded Reader Programme at TUS. Briefly, MReader (formerly Moodle Reader) is a website created in the mid-2000s by Thomas Robb, a professor at Kyoto Sangyo University, which stores a massive 6,500+ graded reader quizzes (Robb, n.d. (a)), and designed for the greatest extent of user friendliness, administrative ease and academic security. As noted, these three factors cannot always maximally coexist (Robb, n.d. (b)).

At the outset of the course, students are given a placement exam

which will provide the instructor an informed idea about which graded reader level each student should be placed. This is especially important at TUS where reading courses are not streamed via placement exams. The MReader administrator for the class can set the levels within which student is constrained to select their books and only quizzes for books within a given student's level will be accessible for that student. This feature is especially important because it ensures that students do not make the common error of ambitiously attempting to read above their current level. Setting the levels goes a long way in ensuring that students receive the greatest possible amount of Krashen's (1983) comprehensible

Kyoto Level	TOEIC	TOEFL
Starter	200	300
Level 1	250	350
Level 2	280	365
Level 3	320	380
Level 4	380	400
Level 5	450	430
Level 6	500	450

Figure 2. MReader Kyoto Scale TOEIC/TOEFL Conversion

Reader series written for language learners			
Starter	Foundation Series-Levels 1,2,3 BlackCat EasyReads Level 1	Building Blocks Library Level 5	Oxford Classic Tales B1,B2
Level 1	Foundation Series-Levels 4,5 Building Blocks Library Level 6	Oxford Bookworms Starter Page Turners Level 1	Penguin Readers Easystart Macmillan Starter
	BlackCat EasyReads Level 2	Scholastic Popcorn 1	Oxford Classic Tales E1
Level 2	Foundation Series-Levels 6,7 BlackCat EasyReads Level 3	Page Turners Level 2 Building Blocks Library Level 7	Penguin Readers Level 1 Macmillan Beginner
	Oxford Dominoes Starter	Scholastic Starter	Scholastic Popcorn 2 Oxford Classic Tales E2
Level 3	Cambridge Starter Helbling Level 1	Page Turners Level 3 Building Blocks Library Level 8	Penguin Readers Level 2 Oxford Classic Tales E3
	BlackCat EasyReads Levels 4,5 Helbling Readers 1	Scholastic Level 1	Scholastic Popcorn 2
Level 4	Cambridge Level 1 Helbling Level 2	Oxford Bookworms Stage 1 Page Turners Level 4,5	Cengage Footprints 800 Building Blocks Library Level 9
	BlackCat GreenApple Starter Helbling Readers 2	BlackCat R&T Stage 1	Compass Classics 1 Oxford Dominoes 1
Level 5	Cambridge Level 2 Helbling Level 3	Oxford Bookworms Stage 2 Page Turners Level 6	Penguin Readers Level 3 Macmillan Elementary
	BlackCat GreenApple Level 1 Helbling Readers 3	BlackCat R&T Stage 2 Oxford Dominoes 2	Cengage Footprints 1000 Compass Classics 2
Level 6	Cambridge Level 3 Helbling Level 4	Oxford Bookworms Stage 3	Oxford Dominoes 3 Compass Classics 3
	BlackCat GreenApple Level 2 Helbling Readers 4	BlackCat R&T Stage 3 Page Turners Level 7,8	Scholastic Level 3 Cengage Footprints 1300
Level 7	Cambridge Level 4 Helbling Readers 5	Oxford Bookworms Stage 4 BlackCat R&T Stage 4	Penguin Readers Level 4 Macmillan Pre-Intermediate
	Cengage Footprints 1600,1900 Cambridge Level 5	Page Turners Level 9,10 Oxford Bookworms Stage 5	Compass Classics 4 Penguin Readers Level 5
Level 8	Cengage Footprints 2200,2600 Cengage Footprints 3000	BlackCat R&T Stage 5 Page Turners Level 11	Macmillan Intermediate Compass Classics 5
	Page Turners Level 12	Oxford Bookworms Stage 6 BlackCat R&T Stage 6	Macmillan Upper-Intermediate Compass Classics 6
Native speaker /young reader series and youth literature			
Starter	Oxford Reading Tree Stage 5		
Level 1	Oxford Reading Tree Stages 6,7	Henry and Mudge	I Can Read Level 1
Level 2	I Can Read Level 2	All Aboard Reading Level 2	Step Into Reading 3
	Oxford Reading Tree Stages 8,9		
Level 3	Marvin Redpost	Nate the Great	Step Into Reading 4
	Magic Tree House	Rainbow Magic	Step Into Reading 5
Level 4	A to Z Mysteries	Cam Jensen	Tashi
	Secret Seven	Zack	Terry Deary's Historical Fiction
Level 5	Quickreads	Junie B. Jones	The Secrets of Droon
	Amber Brown	Judy Moody	Mr Majeika
Level 6	Grosset & Dunlap Who Was...?	Franny K. Stein	Dragon Slayer's Academy
	Fastback Series	Babysitter's Club	
Level 7	Naughtiest Girl	Judy Blume	Bunnica Catwings
	Famous Five		
Level 8	Hardy Boys	Nancy Drew	And many more!

Figure 1. The MReader Kyoto Scale

input (Mikulecky, 2011).

In this way, by reading with increased fluency at a level just at or slightly below their current level students achieve higher numbers of words per minute, students are more likely to achieve a greater fluency and deeper comprehension of texts than they would if they had been reading an inappropriately levelled text. Moreover, using the MReader website, as students pass quizzes, they are slowly promoted to higher reading levels on the MReader Kyoto Scale.

The Kyoto Scale is a useful tool, which unifies the widely varying numeric level designations of the major publishers of graded readers.

Implementing MReader

Implementing MReader into the reading classes at Tokyo University of Science proved to be a somewhat difficult process. A fair number of professors were apprehensive about adopting a new reading program into classes they had been teaching for many years. This arguably neophobic response was perhaps more pronounced among the professors who had been teaching reading classes at TUS longer. It is assumed this response was the result of a self-assessed feeling of established methodology, and a resulting unwillingness to attempt a new, unknown pedagogical method.

Another issue we faced which perhaps could have ameliorated the unwillingness of some lecturers to adopt this new program was a reticence of the department to give us a proper forum to introduce the program through presentation, or other means. This perhaps made the program seem under-supported or relegated to a fringe program; potentially increasing the perception that it could easily be ignored or dismissed. Although most teachers were amenable to implementing the program in their classes, it is conceivable that if the administrators had been given a forum to present the program in full detail, a wider number of teachers would have been onboard with employing the program in their classes.

In the future, it is our hope that through acculturation and acclimation, this program will seem less alienating and more less of an imposition for prospective teachers. This is merely speculative and could be the focus of future research.

Pitfalls Encountered During Implementation

By taking the quizzes at this site, students demonstrate that they have read and comprehended the grader reader which they have just read. Quizzes are comprised of 15 comprehension questions and are timed so that students cannot search the book for answers rather than actually read it. Moreover, if two students take the quizzes together, each mutually piggybacking on the other, the proximity of the IP address along with the time at which the quizzes were taken together will be detected and a notice will be sent to the administrator and/or teacher. Each quiz contains a bank of several dozen questions, making it difficult for students to pass on answers to a quiz for any given graded reader.

Since the MReader allows only one quiz to be taken per-book/per-student, it was our hope that the program could be customized to allow multiple retakes. Although the website stridently cautioned against allowing users to take retakes, given the general intelligence and professionalism of TUS students, we were willing to try out the idea of

allowing retakes. The MReader website perspicuously states in the question-and-answer section that retakes are ill-advised; stated as follows:

Q: Why can my students only take a specific quiz once?

A: The system is made so that students can take any specific quiz only once. We consider it bad pedagogy to allow them to take it more than one time because the purpose of the quiz is to determine whether they read the book or not. If students know that they can have a 2nd or 3rd chance, many of the less motivated students will do the minimum, see if they can pass and then try again after they have read it a bit more.

Despite our wish to customize the program, we soon discovered many cases of precisely the kind of activity about which the website had warned us. The problems we have encountered, which will be discussed briefly, can be described as following: gaming the system/multiple retakes; taking multiple level tests under the same title; and taking tests with the fortitude of prior knowledge, i.e. science students taking basic science book tests.

(1) Gaming the system

Soon after starting the program, we noticed that some students were gaming the system through multiple retakes. Since students only require a 60% score to pass, students would sometimes take the same quiz 20-30 times until they passed by sheer luck. This clearly being a poor metric to evaluate students' book reading, it was decided to implement a "cool down" period of 1-hour being retakes. This slowed down the abuses but did not solve the problem. As a result, it was decided to remove quiz retaking altogether in the following semester.

(2) Same Title Retakes

As we did not have a fully adequate library of graded reader books, we had to allow students to read and take quizzes outside of their level. As a result of this insufficient book collection, we had students taking quizzes for one book in multiple levels. Some students would read a

specific book and then take the corresponding quiz in every level. This misrepresented the number of words they actually read.

(3) Prior-knowledge Quiz Taking

It was noted that several students with advanced knowledge of science were selecting very rudimentary science book quizzes. It is assumed that these quizzes could be passed by science students without reading the corresponding graded reader book, but it is difficult to say whether the students read the books. It is possible that the students chose science-related books simply through an interest in their field, but their prior-knowledge cannot be overlooked. This was especially true in cases where students chose multiple books on very basic science concepts. Since the students could, presumably, pass the tests without looking at the book, we felt it was a potential method of gaining points in the word-count without actually reading.

Practical Reservations and Logistical Problems

A significant reservation we had about running the program as Thomas Robb suggested was that we felt it may discourage students. Since our over-reigning goal was to have students develop a passion for reading books in English, it was thought that allowing students to retake failed quizzes would remove the discouragement of failing, and instead place the focus on the enjoyment of reading. Also, because we wanted to allow a certain level of ease on the part of the participating teachers, we assigned Sakellarios the role of Mreader administrator for all classes. This unintentionally may have limited some teacher autonomy in running the program.

Allowing retakes also presented us with a logistical problem with regards to the administration duties. As some students had taken dozens of retakes of the same book, each retake had to be manually reset in the students' respective profiles. This would often require hours of tedious administrator duties, clicking boxes and resetting many dozens of quizzes

daily. Thomas Robb was contacted to inquire about a feature which would allow us to reset failed quizzes en masse, but he informed me that this was intentionally not included to discourage the practice of allowing multiple retakes. Having the benefit of hindsight, we can now understand the pedagogical and administrative benefits of not including such a feature.

Future Goals

(1) More teacher autonomy/self-administration

Considering we are piloting this programme, we did not want to overwhelm teachers with administrative responsibilities. Much to our surprise, we found many teachers wishing to learn more about the program and how to take on a more active role in running the program. Indeed, it may be important for teachers to feel a certain sense of autonomy with regards to how they wish to incorporate the program in their classrooms. More research needs to be conducted to see if teacher autonomy encourages greater usage of the MReader program.

(2) Larger library selection allowing for proper student levelling

We are very fortunate to be supported by the university and the university library program. In this regard, we are allowed a budget for acquiring books each year. This budget has allowed us to build up the program substantially. Our intention is to continue building the program to increase books in each level, further enabling administrators to constrain students within their specific levels.

(3) Stricter enforcement of failed quizzes

As mentioned earlier in this paper, allowing multiple retakes of quizzes proved to be a mistake in practice. The piloting of the MReader program allowed us to notice our mistake and correct it in the future.

(4) More classes/Higher teacher-participation

As Kipling (2017) found in her trialing of the MReader program at Kanda University of International studies, “class type and teacher involvement both had a big influence on the level of participation in the MReader program”. As our classes were of only one type (reading classes), no difference was observed with regards to class type. As for teacher participation, Kipling’s observation is consistent with our own experience running the program at TUS. The teachers who interacted with the program and MReader admin seemed to have greater participation among students. More research is needed to discuss the mechanism of this phenomenon in greater detail.

It is our hope that more opportunities to instruct teachers on MReader usage will encourage greater participation in future classes. This leads to our final goal:

(5) More opportunities to instruct students and teachers on MReader usage

In order to encourage teacher-and-student understanding of the program, and presumably strengthening a willingness to participate in the administering of MReader, it may be useful to have a platform to explain the program in some detail. We feel the program’s simplicity is not fully understood at first glance and may in fact seem more daunting than it is in actuality. It is our hope that understanding the program will reduce any concerns about the complexity of adopting the program, and presumably empower teachers to use the program with a certain level of ease.

As Kipling further states in her research:

To improve how ER and MReader are introduced to students (and thereby encourage student buy-in), introductory classes need to be developed to explain the benefits of ER in general (specifically, consistent reading over time, as opposed to cramming at the beginning or end of the semester), and to scaffold how students can access and take tests using the MReader platform. This could

involve teachers working closely with a whole class group using a ‘class set’ graded reader at the beginning of the first semester, in order to model how the system works. A standardised word target and grading rubric may also encourage ER and MReader to be taken more seriously. (Kipling, 2017, p. 146)

A forum for explaining the system of MReader would almost assuredly alleviate concerns about the difficulty of incorporating the program in the classroom of TUS educators. It is our hope that in the future, such a platform will be available for teachers wishing to encourage graded reading in TUS classes.

Endnotes

- 1) Moore (1943) notes that some detractors of extensive reading believe that by promoting inferencing skills, that learners may adopt the view that a rough, incomplete, or slightly inaccurate comprehension of words may suffice, and they are concerned that this will lead to an “unscientific attitude toward language study” (p. 7).

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